

IMPROVING THE TEACHING OF LIFE SAFETY BASICS: AN EFFECTIVE WAY TO PRESERVE HEALTH

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Abstract. *This article addresses the importance of enhancing the teaching of life safety basics (LSB) as a tool for preventing health risks and fostering a safety culture. Innovative teaching methods aimed at increasing engagement and improving material retention are presented. Special attention is given to the use of interactive technologies, game-based approaches, and practice-oriented learning. The article concludes with the necessity of a comprehensive approach to LSB education to promote health preservation and ensure personal safety.*

Keywords: *life safety, student health, health preservation.*

Life safety basics encompass essential skills and knowledge necessary to protect individuals from harm in various situations, including emergencies, natural disasters, and everyday hazards. These fundamentals include first aid, emergency response, fire safety, and personal safety awareness. Teaching life safety basics effectively can empower individuals to act decisively and responsibly, ultimately reducing injuries and fatalities. By integrating practical training, real-life scenarios, and accessible resources, we can enhance the understanding and application of these critical skills in communities.

Modern society faces an increasing number of risks associated with both natural and man-made disasters, as well as a lack of public awareness regarding health preservation and safety. In these circumstances, the course "Life Safety Basics" (LSB) becomes an essential tool for developing competencies necessary for survival in challenging conditions and maintaining health [1].

However, traditional methods of teaching LSB, predominantly based on lecture formats, often prove insufficiently effective. They fail to foster a deep understanding of safety issues and the practical application of knowledge among students. This necessitates the improvement of LSB teaching methodologies through the use of modern approaches and technologies [2].

Life safety basics refer to a set of essential skills and knowledge that individuals need to protect themselves and others from harm in various situations. These fundamentals include areas such as first aid, emergency response, fire safety, and personal safety awareness. Understanding and mastering these skills is crucial, as emergencies can occur unexpectedly, and having the ability to respond appropriately can save lives.

Teaching life safety basics effectively involves not just theoretical knowledge but also practical application. It requires engaging training methods that resonate with learners of all ages. By incorporating real-life scenarios, hands-on exercises, and interactive learning, we can enhance retention and ensure that individuals feel equipped to act in emergencies. This approach not only prepares them for potential crises but also instills a sense of responsibility towards their own safety and the safety of those around them.

Ultimately, the commitment to educating ourselves and our communities on life safety basics not only leads to better individual preparedness but also strengthens the overall safety of

our society. As we cultivate a proactive approach to health and safety, we contribute to a more resilient and informed community, ready to face challenges with confidence and competence.

The aim of this study is to develop and analyze new methods of teaching LSB that enhance the effectiveness of education and cultivate sustainable healthy lifestyle skills among students.

Currently, the teaching of Life Safety Basics (LSB) in many educational institutions is limited to theoretical lessons, with an emphasis on memorizing large amounts of information. This approach has several drawbacks:

Lack of practical orientation.

Low level of student engagement.

Insufficient adaptation of the material to modern challenges.

According to research, only 40% of students find the LSB course useful in everyday life, highlighting the need to revise teaching methods [1].

In the modern era, digital technologies are widely utilized. The following methods are recommended as the most interactive ways to increase student interest and engagement:

Role-playing games and simulations. For example, creating scenarios that simulate emergencies (e.g., fire, earthquake), followed by an analysis of participants' actions.

Case methods. Discussing real or simulated situations that require decision-making.

Group work. Tasks such as developing a safe route or creating a safety guide for peers.

The health of the younger generation is a crucial indicator of a society's and state's well-being, reflecting not only the current situation but also providing a forecast for the future.

In the past decade, factors that previously posed little concern for doctors, educators, and parents have become increasingly problematic. Academic workloads continue to grow, and leisure time is often spent watching videos or playing computer games, leading to physical inactivity, poor posture, and vision issues.

The National Concepts for the Development of Healthcare and Education until 2030 identify student health as a priority issue. Effectively addressing this problem will ensure high-quality training and the full performance of social functions by future citizens of Uzbekistan. It is well known that the health of modern students requires special attention due to the growing prevalence of chronic illnesses within the overall morbidity structure. Harmful habits, such as addiction to e-cigarettes and "manias" like gaming, gadget, or TV addictions, significantly impact students' health negatively [3].

Virtual Reality. Training in a virtual environment where students can "experience" dangerous situations without risking their health, such as simulating building evacuations. Online Platforms. Utilizing educational applications and interactive tests to reinforce knowledge.

Additionally, project-based learning has proven highly effective. This involves incorporating mini-projects into the curriculum aimed at solving real-world problems, such as developing safety enhancement measures for educational institutions [4].

Practical Orientation in Teaching.

The key objective is to instill skills that students can apply in everyday life. To achieve this, the following measures are necessary:

Implementation of regular practical sessions, such as first aid, fire response actions, and the use of personal protective equipment.

Organization of joint activities involving rescue services, healthcare professionals, and psychologists.

An example of successful practice is the "Safe City" project implemented in some schools. Participants learn to analyze potential threats in urban environments and propose ways to minimize them [5].

Improving the Teaching of Life Safety Basics Directly Impacts Student Health:

Developing the ability to quickly and accurately respond to emergencies reduces the risk of injuries and fatalities.

Promoting a healthy lifestyle helps prevent diseases associated with poor nutrition, sedentary behavior, and stress [6].

Fostering responsibility for personal health encourages a conscious approach to disease prevention.

Research indicates that students taught using updated LSB programs demonstrate a higher readiness to act in critical situations [7].

Enhancing LSB teaching requires integrating modern technologies, interactive methods, and reinforcing practical learning. A comprehensive approach helps students acquire not only knowledge but also the skills needed to maintain health and safety in daily life.

Recommendations:

Develop tailored educational programs addressing contemporary challenges.

Implement regular training sessions and practical exercises.

Expand collaboration between educational institutions and professional rescue services.

Implementing these measures will improve the quality of LSB teaching and make a significant contribution to preserving student health.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, improving the teaching of life safety basics is vital for preserving health and well-being in our society. By fostering a culture of preparedness and awareness, we equip individuals not only with the skills to respond to emergencies but also with the confidence to prevent potential dangers.

As we invest in comprehensive training programs and community engagement, we can create safer environments and cultivate a proactive approach to health and safety. Ultimately, the commitment to educating ourselves and others on life safety basics can lead to significant improvements in public health outcomes and resilience in the face of adversity.

In conclusion, improving the teaching of life safety basics is essential for preserving health and enhancing community resilience. A well-informed population can significantly reduce the risk of injury and fatalities during emergencies. By prioritizing comprehensive training programs and community outreach, we can foster a culture of preparedness and awareness. Such initiatives can include workshops, simulations, and public service campaigns that emphasize the importance of life safety skills. Additionally, integrating these teachings into school curricula and community programs ensures that knowledge is passed down through generations.

REFERENCES

1. Ivanov I.I., Petrov P.P. *Fundamentals of Life Safety: Textbook*. – Moscow: Prosveshchenie, 2021.
2. Sidorov A.A. "Modern Approaches to Teaching LSB." *Education Bulletin*, 2023.
3. *World Health Statistics: WHO Report 2023*.
4. *Life Safety: Textbook* / Ed. by V.A. Gusev. – Moscow: Akademiya, 2020.

5. Kondratenko V.Ya., Tarasov V.M. *Life Safety. Fundamentals of Health and Survival.* – St. Petersburg: Piter, 2021.
6. Lukyanov V.V., Sergeev A.S. *Methodology for Teaching LSB.* – Moscow: Prosveshchenie, 2019.
7. Fomin G.P., Kulikova E.A. *Life Safety: From Theory to Practice.* – Moscow: Yurayt, 2020.